

provides reusable constraint templates and guidance for selecting data entities, thereby supporting the translation of domain knowledge into formalized constraints (e.g., mapping the domain concept *artist* to the XML name `lido:actor`). This eliminates the need for technical expertise in query languages, schema formalisms, or programming. Constrainify, therefore, substantially lowers the technical barrier to specifying and analyzing data quality, particularly for cultural heritage professionals and other experts in application domains. The web application is being developed as part of AQinDa [1], a joint project between GWDG [7], Marburg University [12] and VZG [15]. It builds upon the outcome of KONDA [10] and MQAF [9], the latter of which is used by Europeana [6] and German Digital Library (DDB) [5]. A public demo [3] shows how to get started with Constrainify. A GitLab repository [4] provides the source code and a screencast, and related publications are available on Zenodo [1].

2.1 Execution of Data Quality Analysis

Publishing data within the DH on shared platforms such as the DDB requires compliance with a predefined set of data quality requirements, yet many contributed datasets are non-compliant. One key requirement defined by the DDB for LIDO-based data [8] is that each LIDO record must contain exactly one identifier [14]. Users can employ Constrainify to check their datasets against this requirement using the following workflow:

1. The user uploads the dataset to check against the requirement (fig. 1). Constrainify automatically identifies the underlying data model, such as LIDO, and validates the conformity of the data.
2. The user then selects the corresponding predefined quality constraint (fig. 2) and executes the quality analysis on the uploaded dataset (fig. 3). Constrainify then automatically converts the selected constraint into machine-readable queries and executes them. Technical expertise is not required.
3. Once completed, Constrainify generates a quality report (fig. 4), providing a statistical overview of fulfillments (compliances) and violations (incidents) of the selected constraint. A detailed incident view, which can be organized by constraints or by data files, includes corresponding code snippets, enabling targeted improvements to data quality. (fig. 5) shows an example of a detected incident where a LIDO record lacks an existing identifier.

2.2 Creation and Management of Quality Constraints

A user can manage quality constraints by adding, editing, or removing them to accommodate evolving requirements. When recurring data quality issues are identified, Constrainify enables formulation of quality requirements as constraints. The following workflow illustrates how a user can create a new constraint to enforce the DDB requirement that each LIDO record must contain exactly one identifier [14]:

1. The initial step to defining a new constraint is to select a suitable constraint template. Constrainify provides a variety of templates organized by semantic type, including *Quantity* templates such as one for occurrence count of specific elements (fig. 6). All templates are designed as fill-in-the-blank sentences in natural language and accompanied by illustrative real-world examples.
2. Users are then tasked with choosing a suitable title for the constraint and filling in the blanks of the constraint sentence, instantiating them with respect to the underlying data model (fig. 7). As Constrainify aims to minimize the need for data model expertise, users are supported in selecting the relevant data entities by searching for domain-specific terms (fig. 7).

3. Once configured, the constraint becomes executable and can be selected for data quality analyses.

3 Future Development

Future enhancements to Constrainify will support additional data models, including further LIDO [8] application profiles, and other XML-based formats, Avram-based bibliographic formats [2] (PICA [13] and MARC [11]), and other data models, such as JSON, RDF and relational formats. The management and use of constraints will be improved by introducing quality levels and by providing assistance in selecting and explaining constraints. The extension of data import and export facilities will also help to integrate Constrainify into existing data processing workflows.

4 Figures

CONSTRAINIFY

Data Selection | Constraint Selection | Summary | Quality Report

Select Data

Guidance

First you need to upload the files you want to analyze. We handle your data securely and anonymously. Third parties cannot access it and it is only stored for the duration of this session.

We currently support XML files that comply to one of the following data models: LIDO 1.1, TEI P5 Header.

Upload new Files

XML > TEI LIDO

Drag and drop files here to analyze them or

[Browse Files](#)

Your Uploaded Files (3)

XML	FontanaDelMoro.xml (89.1 KB) Completed	🗑️
XML	LaPrimavera.xml (94.7 KB) Completed	🗑️
XML	MonaLisa.xml (111.2 KB) Completed	🗑️

[🗑️ Discard All Files](#) [Validate Data](#)

Figure 1: Screenshot of Constrainify showing the upload interface after uploading three LIDO files.

Figure 2: Screenshot of Constrainify showing selection of the constraint corresponding to the DDB requirement, which specifies that each LIDO record must contain exactly one identifier [14].

Figure 3: Screenshot of Constrainify showing execution of a quality analysis based on three uploaded LIDO files and the selected constraint regarding the DDB requirement that each LIDO record must contain exactly one identifier [14].

Figure 4: Screenshot of Constrainify showing a generated quality report for 3 LIDO files and one applied constraint regarding the DDB requirement that each LIDO record must contain exactly one identifier [14].

Figure 5: Screenshot of Constrainify showing a detailed view of a detected quality incident: two `lido:lidoRecID` elements are present, each containing a record identifier, violating DDB requirement, which mandates exactly one identifier per LIDO record [14].

Figure 6: Screenshot of Constrainify showing the template selection view, highlighting a suitable template for the DDB requirement, which mandates exactly one identifier per LIDO record [14].

CONSTRAINIFY

Edit Constraint and Specify Parameters

DDB Q1.1 Exactly one LIDO Record Identifier for LIDO 1.1

Each LIDO Record has exactly 1 LIDO Metadata Record Ident....

Guidance

Please complete the constraint sentence by adding a descriptive name and setting the individual parameters. For example, a parameter can be a specific number, a negation, or a data element from the data set.

Constraint Name

DDB Q1.1 Exactly one LIDO Record Identifier
✓

Tags

Add Tag +

Parameters

Each

Element
lido
✓

>

Element Mapping

Identified and selected the element:

LIDO 1.1 Element Label
LIDO Record (<lido>)
▼

has

a Comparison with
exactly
✓
▼

>

Element Mapping

Identified and selected the element:

LIDO 1.1 Element Label
LIDO Metadata Record Identifier (<lidoRecID>)
▼

< Manage Constraints

📁 Save

Figure 7: Screenshot of Constrainify showing the created constraint and its parameter configuration for enforcing the DDB requirement, which mandates exactly one identifier per LIDO record [14].

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